

An Innovation Searching for Enhancing the China Foreign Trade
Trillion Yuan provinces Value & Chinese Master Graduated Application
Number on Scientists Sustainably

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ABSTRACT: As an indicator to nations economy development the GDP (gross domestic product) has an important influence to the economy level, quality aspects etc., so the comparing with other continents will have a significant meaning continuously by scientists who publish their latest achievement at the high impact-factor journal within a periodic time. We should look at the paper through internet web site even we can download the article for seeing later for the sake of erecting reading habits and information from there. Thereby, the one in journal will become a bridge connecting the readers and authors where the new method, approach may be seen by us. So that the high-technology product is able to be produced with those innovation method accounting for certain meaning new products which may stimulus the presently searching and producing ones because there is so thorough investigation to one property. We should continue to process those key parameter searching activity so that new functional product enables to be created in light of insistence and resilience

measures. On the other hand, new quality productivity will be pushed from laboratory to industrial business like photovoltaic one, vehicle battery, hydrogen fuel etc. field, which may increase the corresponding industrial substitution those old energy usefulness for new quality energy. All of them may form the new industrial innovation with new transiting energy product which occupies the industrial production more and more. In future those new energy like generating the electrical amount has to dominate more ratio in GDP value. We must rapidly and urgently promote the new quality productivity from university lab to institution and industrial business for the sake of transforming the innovation energy into society quickly. On the other side, the more attracting the excellent talents from overseas university, institution & industry business will be done by us from now on. In light of News report the China R & D (research & development) investment ratio is gradually increasing year by year, so there is more chance and good equipment can match to proceed the new high-tech product preliminary investigation and promotion by recruiting others like USA top scientists who can transfer the USA top technique to China. We should go on processing those talents turn-back work from famous university etc. in abroad like USA accounting for new environmental formality to become the leadership role now.

Keywords: *innovation; search for; China foreign trade trillion yuan provinces; Chinese Master graduated application number.*

1. Introduction

The nations & regions GDP will represent their comprehensive strength in views of economy level and quality, so searching it may have an important effectiveness for us to process statistic with the national producing amount every month, season and year. In the meantime, the value with y-y has also a significant meaning that reflects the economy growth step because we should clarify the increasing change so as to evaluate the increasement and declination value preciously. The positive y-y value may mean the good and rapid economy developing status whilst the minus one may state the bad and slow economy step. So we judge the economy developing enhancement and decreasement through that y-y value for a certain period. Thereby, the detail discussion will include in the following aspects. The GDP which indicates

national economic status has provided an important role in every aspect in the world. So that the population increasing rate would be maintained for the sake of raising high-technique product with the entire industrial chain constantly which might enhance our new-quality-productivity. Hence we should consider the effective factors for example the population quantity, new quality productivity with high- technique etc. like big plane electric vehicle battery AI robot quantum computer medicine making disease diagnosis AI (artificial intelligence), ocean source space exploration nuclear generator etc. other ones. Low population is enable to offer high life & quality with improving GDP per capita value. Meanwhile, it can enhance the national whole GDP value and help us to boost the economic recovery and many things to do. So the certain population is about to improve our national confidence some degree and make us to become priority one as early as possible even the super-country to lead the world to leadership right.

In contrast, the GDP increasing rate may play a significant role with regulating population increasing rate mutually and cooperatively. Hence the two aspects may be emphasized and paid attention to in thriving the whole national economic developed degree through enough wielding our generations positively and efficiently by our government institution endeavor and evaluation. For the sake of making relevant policies and allocating capital into the necessary industries the corresponding strategic plan needs to be made under various background and entities. Then the according monitor and estimation will be followed and estimated periodically and frequently by the observer in government's institution. At last as to the developed speed in one nation the corresponding population increasing quantity and high-technique product producing will be discussed and considered more preciously and correctly according to the near past years experience and variation.

Therefore, the high-technique products will be completed through wielding our scientist & senior Engineers coordination tightly for the sake of reviving the industrial and tertiary modernization. We should constantly look for and seek the new quality productivity sustainably so as to take place of our traditional industry becoming modernity. An innovation industry like new energy electric generator will be in front of our path forwards, so that the corresponding tactic must be put up and

seek the opportunity and fortune in order to burden our responsibility quickly and not to forget recommend the fitting one to appoint new occupation. Like the Bole identified horse or Maosui self-recommended the recommendation will be represent one aspect for our human resource department to consider and evaluate the recommended included a full research room with a set of computer high-technique instrument & device, subordinate, subsidiary staff, salary, house, welfare etc. a series of work so as to appoint his new occupation reasonably and willingly. [1~20]

2. Discussions

The enhancing GDP behaviors will be meaning regulating the one for matching new dynamic balance according to exhibiting new tendency like War, disease and political fringe conflict which affect our life for a certain economic developing degree. So that the judgement may be according to the met actual situation making a corresponding method like increasing & decreasing this year or next one anticipating value so as to alleviate the nation burdens. Thereby, the fitting value may be satisfying the domestic consumption demands in order to rise up the positive consumption that will help us to go through the difficult situation when the risk happen. On the other side, the foreign trade will be encouraged so that the exportation win the importation for the sake of acquiring corresponding foreign reservation that is to be essential in critical period like when we buy some necessary goods abroad like military and defence weapon and equipment when we meet difficulty. Presently the high-technique product like drones and low air economy demands us to wield more powerful role in delivering the package and taking-out brisker and quicker that enable form the automatic and artificial intelligence service in big cities completed by robots from the reserve-box to each floor offices directly. So we look at the convenience and security. We should continuously to search for the new automatic & artificial intelligence robot work function special in the humanoid ones. [21~22]

2.1 The Chinese Master graduated application number

The Chinese Master graduated application number in 2020~2026 might show 343~341 thousand students in 2020~2026 accordingly to exhibit first increasement by 2023 and declination situation from 474 thousand to now in light of Figure 1.

Figure 1 The Chinese Master graduated application number in 2020~2026. [1]

Meanwhile, the Chinese Master graduated recruitment number in 2020~2024 might show 99~118 thousand students in 2024 accordingly to exhibit increasement situation whilst the recruitment rate declination a little from 28% thousand to 25% now in light of Figure 2 in those years.

Figure 2 The Chinese Master graduated recruitment number in 2020~2024. [1]

2.2 China foreign trade trillion-yuan provinces

The Chinese foreign trade beyond trillion analysis might show 930 & 940 billion yuan by Shanghai & Jiangsu in 2003 in light of Figure 3 to explain their strong foreign trade capacity. The y-y value would indicate 55% & 76% accordingly by them expressed their most forwards steps.

Figure 3 The Chinese foreign trade beyond trillion analysis. [2]

On the other side, the Chinese foreign trade beyond trillion analysis might show 2,340 & 560 billion yuan by Guangzhou & Beijing in 2003 in light of Figure 4 to explain the Guangdong province strong foreign trade capacity. The y-y value would indicate 23% & 25% accordingly by them expressed their more forwards development steps.

Figure 4 The Chinese foreign trade beyond trillion analysis. [2]

2.3 Introduction to the Nescafe coffee

The Nescafe powder coffee is classified as super-concentration and low-sugar that does not include zero trans fat. Its composition includes as like in Table 1. The

usefulness is adding 150ml & 85°C water into 13g powder to mixed averagely drink with maintaining the heat. The expiration date is 16 months.[3]

Table 1. The nutrient of Nesacfe power.

Nutrients	Rate, per 100ml
Energy	152 KJ
Protein	0g
Fat	1.3g
Zero trans fat	0g
Carbon-hydrate	6.1g
Sugar	4.7g
Natrium	63mg

3. Conclusions

As an indicator to nations economy development the GDP (gross domestic product) has an important influence to the economy level, quality aspects etc., so the comparing with other continents will have a significant meaning continuously by scientists who publish their latest achievement at the high impact-factor journal within a periodic time. We should look at the paper through internet web site even we can download the article for seeing later for the sake of erecting reading habits and information from there. Thereby, the one in journal will become a bridge connecting the readers and authors where the new method, approach may be seen by us. So that the high-technology product is able to be produced with those innovation method accounting for certain meaning new products which may stimulus the presently searching and producing ones because there is so thorough investigation to one property. We should continue to process those key parameter searching activity so that new functional product enables to be created in light of insistence and resilience measures. On the other hand, new quality productivity will be pushed from laboratory to industrial business like photovoltaic one, vehicle battery, hydrogen fuel etc. field, which may increase the corresponding industrial substitution those old energy usefulness for new quality energy. All of them may form the new industrial innovation with new transiting energy product which occupies the industrial production more and more. In future those new energy like generating the electrical

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declared that there were not conflicts of interest to disclose.

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